

DUTIES OF THE TEACHER IN PRE-SCHOOL EDUCATION

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Abstract: This article examines the tasks of educators in preschool educational institutions, their contribution to child development, as well as the responsibilities of educators based on modern pedagogical approaches. The personal, intellectual and social development of children is directly dependent on the work of the educator in the educational process. Also, the article analyzes the tasks of educators in increasing the child's self-confidence, forming his interest in education and helping him socialize.

Key words: preschool education, educator, child development, pedagogy, teacher tasks, educational process.

Introduction.

Preschool education serves as a foundation for a child's future successful development. During this period, the child not only acquires knowledge and skills, but also begins to form his personality and social skills. Educators play a leading role in this process. The main task of the educator in preschool educational institutions is to develop all abilities of children, prepare them for the social environment and take into account their individual needs. An educator helps children develop not only intellectually, but also emotionally and socially, and also plays a major role in preparing children for the future educational process.

Methodology:

The research analyzed the activities of educators in preschool educational institutions. Through the questionnaire and interview methods, the teachers' methods of performing their duties, pedagogical approaches and their impact on the child's development were studied. Through the analysis of literature, additional information about the tasks of educators was collected based on modern educational technologies and methods. Teachers and parents working with preschool children were selected as the target group.

The main duties of an educator:

Duties of the educator cover several main areas:

Training and development:

The educator conducts teaching activities to develop children's intellectual and cognitive abilities. In this process, children are given various knowledge, such as learning letters and sounds, drawing, and forming mathematical

concepts. Through lessons and games, educators develop children's attention, memory, and creative abilities.

Supporting personal and social development:

One of the important tasks of an educator is to increase children's personal self-confidence and support the process of socialization. In this process, educators develop the skills of children to communicate, find their place in the team, and express their thoughts. Through team games and activities, children learn to work cooperatively with each other, which helps them find their place in the future society.

Spiritual and moral education:

Moral and spiritual education is of great importance in preschool education. Educators teach children such qualities as respect, honesty, responsibility and kindness. This process is carried out through games, fairy tales and various pedagogical activities.

Ensuring physical development:

Physical development is important for children, and physical exercises and sports events are organized as one of the tasks of the educator. Educators conduct various movement games and exercises for children's physical health, which not only helps them to be healthy, but also helps to develop their physical skills.

Management and organization of the educational process:

Educators make plans and organize activities to ensure the continuity of the educational process and active participation of children in educational activities. Also, educators take into account children's interests and update educational programs on time.

Cooperation with parents:

Cooperation between educators and parents is an important factor for the successful development of children. Educators inform parents about the process of children's development, give recommendations on how to support their development at home.

Discussion:

The tasks of the educator cover various aspects and affect all aspects of the child's development. An educator serves not only as a teacher who gives knowledge, but also as a leader in the process of spiritual, moral, social and physical development of a child. Close cooperation between parents and educators ensures continuous development of children. In this process,

educators' use of modern pedagogical approaches helps to develop the child's creative abilities.

Result:

Educators play an important role in creating a foundation for child development in preschool education. Their pedagogical activity greatly contributes to the intellectual, personal and social development of children. The successful performance of the educator's tasks increases the effectiveness of the educational process and prepares children for future educational stages. Therefore, the professional training and pedagogical competences of educators are of decisive importance in the development of children.

Summary:

In preschool education, the teacher's tasks play a decisive role in the comprehensive development of children. These tasks are aimed not only at expanding children's knowledge, but also at their social, personal and emotional development. The results of the research show that educators have a great responsibility in the process of child development, and they play a key role in preparing children for society, developing their abilities, and forming them as self-confident, independent individuals. Educators work not only as teachers, but also as coaches and guides in the educational process.

Using modern pedagogical approaches and technologies, educators create the necessary conditions for the full development of children's abilities. Also, working in close cooperation with parents increases the success of educators in raising children. This leads to children's success in education and becoming active, socially responsible members of society.

In general, the role of educators in preschool education is very important, and their responsible and quality pedagogical activity directly affects the future education and life success of children.

References:

1. Berk, L. E. (2013). *Child Development*. Boston: Pearson Education.
2. Epstein, J. L. (2001). *School, Family, and Community Partnerships: Preparing Educators and Improving Schools*. Boulder, CO: Westview Press.
3. Shonkoff, J. P., & Phillips, D. A. (2000). *From Neurons to Neighborhoods: The Science of Early Childhood Development*. Washington, DC: National Academy Press.
4. Vygotsky, L. S. (1978). *Mind in Society: The Development of Higher Psychological Processes*. Cambridge, MA: Harvard University Press.
5. Walker, S. P., et al. (2007). *Child Development: Risk Factors for Adverse Outcomes in Developing Countries*. *The Lancet*, 369(9556), 145-157.